

Can Bangladesh cherry-pick from the marine conservation initiatives?

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Abstract

The study was designed to help the Bangladesh Government in framing a national marine policy focusing on conservation and environmental protection. In doing so, this paper evaluated the existing legal, institutional, policy and strategic planning frameworks. The study also examined the progress of achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 14 since 2016, the effectiveness of the protected areas, the emerging anthropogenic-climatic challenges, and the threats and challenges faced by the artisanal fishers. This multidisciplinary research collected both primary and secondary data by applying multiple research approaches. The findings show that the marine regulatory framework is like a mosaic embroidered with the nonexistence of any specific marine law and marine policy, paradoxical allocation of business for the line ministries, jurisdictional overlapping, lack of coordination and integration among the stakeholders, non-compliance with the laws, and conflict of interests. In most of the cases, both conservations and degradations go hand in hand in the protected areas. Bangladesh has made insignificant progress in achieving SDG 14 and has not ensured access for artisanal fishers to marine resources and markets. With the existing regulatory framework, it is hardly possible to cope with the emerging and predicted future anthropogenic-climatic challenges. The study recommends legal reforms and reallocation of business among the line ministries to abolish jurisdictional overlapping and to establish effective marine governance. The study also advocates for making a farsighted strategic plan to combat climate change. A conceptual model of an evidence-based national marine policy has been developed.

Keywords: Marine conservation, jurisdictional overlapping, conflict of interest, protected areas, coordination and integration, marine governance

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is endowed with the incredible ecosystem services of the Bay of Bengal, one of the world's 64 Large Marine Ecosystems, including fish breeding areas, mangroves, coral reefs and estuaries [1]. The *Sundarbans*, the largest contiguous mangrove ecosystem in the world, provides provisioning, regulating and cultural benefits to more than 3 million people [2]. It is a paradise of both terrestrial and aquatic flora and fauna. The presence of mammals, including Bengal Tigers, and many endangered amphibians, reptiles and cetaceans glorifies this mangrove. Up to the beginning of the 19th century, the wild buffalo, swamp deer, hog deer, barking deer, freshwater crocodile, and single-horned and *Javan* rhinoceros roamed through this mangrove [3]. The *Saint Martin's* Coral Island is highly rich with biodiversity and is also the habitat of a few globally threatened marine turtles and many migratory birds [4].

Bangladesh, one of the worst-hit by climate change and one of the most populous countries in the world, is combating anthropogenic-climatic stressors on numerous fronts to protect its marine and coastal biodiversity. These stressors act simultaneously, degrading the diversity, functions and services of the coastal ecosystems. The *Sundarbans* mangrove has been struggling singly against climate change and intensified human pressures at the same time; consequently, the biodiversity is in peril [5]. Incremental land-based pollutions and oil spillage pose a great threat to brackish swamps, mangrove habitats, salt marsh and benthic ecosystems [6]. The biodiversity in the estuaries and the territorial waters in the sea is declining at a faster pace due to the domination of commercial fishermen, suppression of artisanal fishers, over-extraction of living resources and destructive fishing [7, 8]. Over the last few decades, the number of coral species declined from 141 to 41 [9, 10], and it is predicted that by 2045, all coral species will be extinct from *Saint Martin's* Coral Island if the current degradation continues [9]. These declines jeopardize the functional integrity of coastal and marine ecosystems of Bangladesh. Consequently, the protection of marine and coastal floral and faunal species, as well as ecosystems from further degradation, needs an integration of both marine and coastal conservation actions.

In response to the widening apprehension of global and national environmental and conservation threats, Bangladesh signed, agreed, ratified and acceded several conventions, declarations, guidelines and agreements [11] notably “*Ramsar* Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat 1971”; “Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage 1972”; “Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) 1992”; “United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)”; International Maritime Organization Conventions (IMO); “United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED)”; and the “1995 FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries”. Certainly, UNCLOS aimed at creating an integrated marine regulatory framework undermining the fragmented system [12].

Increasing awareness of the importance of the legal and institutional frameworks in regulating the environment and biodiversity over the last decade can be considered as the first hit from Bangladesh [13]. The legal framework that includes acts, ordinances, rules and gazette notifications legitimizing marine and coastal resource management, habitat and biodiversity conservation, and environmental protection [14]. There is no individual law on coastal and

marine resource management and environmental protection, but many elements of these issues are supported by many laws, notably inland laws and a few aged marine laws [11]. Likewise, there is no specific marine policy in Bangladesh, but a few sectoral policies roll out piecemeal. The country has picked up the consolidation of the institutional framework, both conceptually and functionally, over the last decade [13]. Traditionally, the unequivocal authorities of the line ministries implement the overarching and cross-sectoral legislation and policies within the existing framework. Widespread of non-compliances of the laws and policies is common due to institutional weakness, and subsequently, the degradation of marine living resources is quickened on many occasions [11]. Several studies found that fishery-related laws and policies, the institutional mechanisms at the implementation level, and strategies were not properly functional to conserve marine and coastal fisheries [1, 7, 11, 14, 15, and 16]. The absence of marine governance or policy exacerbated marine pollution in Bangladesh by the time mentioned [17]. The existing regulatory regime and the legal framework have failed in ensuring conservation and sustainability of the threatened forests of the *Sundarbans* mangrove shared by Bangladesh [18]. Despite the existence of the legal framework and institutional mechanisms, *Saint Martin's* Coral Island faces the severe degradation of coral reef resources [19]. Marine conservation is blended with marine and terrestrial conservation [20, 21]. Marine conservation unquestionably holds responsibility for the connectivity among the terrestrial, freshwater and marine realms [20]. Therefore, a comprehensive study on regulatory regimes of marine conservation considering all ecosystems has become indispensable. The study aims at analyzing the legal, policy, institutional and strategic planning frameworks. This analysis will help in the identification of the knowledge gap, and existing threats and challenges in preparing a national marine policy, a farsighted strategic planning and a spatial conservation planning. The study will immensely contribute to pinpointing the narrow and broad interfaces, and constrained and diffuse connections among institutions from top to bottom.

As a good performer in achieving the Millennium Development Goals within the stipulated time, Bangladesh has taken various activities in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 [1]. Bangladesh has approved SDG indicator 14.5.1 as a national priority indicator (NPI) for embracing marine conservation [22]. The year 2020 marks the fifth year of implementation of the SDGs. The assessment of the progress in achieving SDG 14 will help Bangladesh in finding the gaps and in speeding up the actions, as it has embraced and institutionalized the goals into its national plans. The role of artisanal fishers is embedded with SDG 14 for the sustainable use of marine resources, ending over-fishing and providing equal access for all to resources and markets. The number of artisanal fishers is continuously decreasing at an alarming rate due to marketing issues, natural calamities and the increasing dominance of commercial fishers [8]. The examination of social, economic, and environmental threats and challenges, and regulatory pitfalls surrounding the livelihoods of artisanal fishers will assist in taking a diverse range of legal and policy-based strategies. Marine conservation prioritizes the protection of habitat from future degradation rather than restoration, considering the cost and success rate in marine environments [55]. In compliance with national and international obligations, Bangladesh has been expanding the protected areas since the 1980s [23]. The success of the protected areas depends on the governance, management practices, surveillance, and compliance with the laws and regulations [24]. An assessment of the effectiveness of the protected areas in Bangladesh has become decisive. With the help of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the Forest Department of Bangladesh (FD) started a co-management approach in 2008 in the ecologically critical areas of *Sundarbans* to enhance biodiversity conservation, taking the

community into the governance [25]. The decadal effectiveness of co-management has not been evaluated yet in the *Sundarbans*, although mixed outcomes are reported from the inland areas [25]. A better understanding of emerging anthropogenic-climatic challenges and their regulatory schemes may contribute to formulating evidence-based national marine policy.

2. Methodology

The study collected both primary and secondary data for the period from November 2018 to April 2020.

2.1. Secondary data

The literature related to the institutional, legal, policy and strategic planning frameworks was reviewed. The existing laws, the rules of business of ministries and divisions, public policies, strategic plans, gazette notifications, and other official documents related to coastal and marine management were analyzed critically to develop background information. The annual reports under the financial years 2016-2018 and the annual performance agreement under the financial year 2019-20 of all ministries were analyzed to measure the progress of achieving SDG 14 since 2016. The data on the initiatives taken by different ministries for harnessing the opportunities of the blue economy was collected from the SDG focal points through personal communications and official correspondence.

The head offices of DF, Department of Fisheries (DOF) and the Department of Environment (DOE) located in the coastal *Chittagong*, *Khulna* and *Barisal* Division were visited to collect secondary data on the protected areas (PAs) especially Wildlife Sanctuary (WS), Dolphin Sanctuary (DS), Ecologically Critical Area (ECA), Marine Protected Area (MPA), World Heritage Site (WHS), *Ramsar* Site (RS), National Park (NP), Reserved Forest (RF) and Eco-park (EP) covering the coastal and marine areas. *Gangamati* Reserved Forest Office, a segment of Sundarbans Reserved Forests, *Kuakata*, *Patuakhali*, was visited to collect information about the conservation status of *Lalkakrar* Char (a shoal of red ghost crab, *Ocypode macrocera*).

2.2. Primary data

The study followed a mixed approach in collecting primary data, including a national consultation workshop, divisional workshop, case studies and key informant interviews (KIs). Workshops, a research approach cater a platform for a researcher in spotting, articulating, and scrutinizing poorly-defined or fuzzy challenges in the research domain [26]. The KII technique is useful for the researcher who faces confusion in concluding and feels the need for experts' opinions [27]. On the other hand, a case study is considered an affordable technique to gain a big picture idea of a complex situation and allows for new and unforeseen issues to emerge [54].

2.2.1. Workshops

Knowing the nuts and bolts of this study, all stakeholders, including the bureaucrats, unveiled the veil, participated actively and supported wholeheartedly in the findings going beyond their traditional approaches. A divisional workshop was conducted in *Khulna* to collect data on the

institutional coordination mechanism at the implementation level; to identify the challenges, including conflict of interest and non-compliance with the laws; and to gather the ideas of alternative income-generating activities avoiding brackish shrimp culture. In total 52 participants attended the workshop including researchers from Life Science School, Khulna University; representatives from the concerned public departments of divisional headquarters; fishermen community leaders from *Mongla Upazilla* (sub-district); senior-level officers of Bangladesh Coast Guard (West Zone); Bangladesh Navy (*Titumir*), *Khulna Shipyard* and *Mongla Port Authority*; Deputy Commissioners (DC) of *Bagerhat*, *Khulna* and *Satkhira* districts; environmental lawyers from the bar council; environmental journalists; launch owners; tour operators; environmental volunteers; public representatives; chamber of commerce; and NGOs working on environmental issues. Following the same motto and modality, another divisional workshop was carried out in *Barisal*, where 57 respondents actively participated. The presence of the Divisional Commissioner, all DCs of the districts under this division, Commanding Officer of Bangladesh Coast Guard (South Zone), fishermen community leaders from *Mohipur*, and researchers from *Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science & Technology University, Patuakhali*, along with other stakeholders, sweetened this workshop. In the national consultation workshop held in Dhaka, a total of 119 participants attended. The SDG focal points of all ministries (not below deputy secretary); retired scholar-bureaucrats; sectoral experts; professionals and researchers from different educational, training and research institutions; environmental lawyers; representatives from Bangladesh Navy, Coast Guard, Tourist Police and River Police; Civil Society; and NGOs were the key participants. The participants were divided into three thematic groups: legal, institutional and policy-strategy. On the ground of the day-to-day activities, the SDG focal points were included in the first group purposively, and they identified the line ministries and divisions having stakes in marine and environment management directly and indirectly. They also scrutinized the respective mandates from the “Rules of Business 1996” and the areas where jurisdictional overlap occurs. The participants of the other two groups were selected based on their choice and expertise. The second group found out the marine and environment-related key and supportive laws, along with the main features, strengths, and weaknesses. The third group identified the marine and environment-related public policies and strategic plan, along with the key features, objectives and loopholes. All of the groups were requested to come up with solutions for overcoming the challenges.

2.2.2. *KKIs*

KKIs were done to collect qualitative data on the emerging challenges due to anthropogenic-climatic stressors. Ten nationally renowned researchers in the field of environment and biodiversity conservation were interviewed to know the causes and consequences of the emerging challenges. Also, five environmental lawyers and an equal number of retired scholar-bureaucrats were selected to find out the regulatory problems in this regard. Beforehand, a loosely structured checklist including a list of issues to be discussed was prepared. A free flow of ideas and information was exchanged during KKIs.

2.2.3. *Case studies*

Four case studies were carried out in four different places of coastal Bangladesh: *Joymonirghol*, *Saint Martin*, *Lalkarar Char* and *Dublar Char*. The cases aimed at identifying the threats, challenges and regulatory problems faced by the protected and reserved areas, and the artisanal

fishermen community. A total of 204 individuals were interviewed using a semi-structured questionnaire in these cases.

Joymonirghol is like a tiny peninsula located at *Mongla Upazilla* under *Bagerhat* district and is considered the mainland nearest to the *Ramsar* Canals, World Heritage Sites and three dolphin sanctuaries of the *Sundarbans* mangrove. This area is under the ecologically critical areas of the *Sundarbans*, where displaced, migrant and landless people reside, and make nests like slums. The dwellers are not affiliated with any institutions, political parties or vested groups. A total of 61 respondents were selected randomly in this case.

Saint Martin (locally known as *Narikel Jinjira*=Coconut Island), the only coral island and an ecologically critical area of Bangladesh, is situated in the northeast part of the Bay of Bengal, about 9 km south of the Cox's *Bazar-Teknaf* peninsula [28] and about 8 km west of the northwest coast of Myanmar. This dumbbell-shaped island, owning only 8 km² of land [29], is connected with a nearby tiny Island during the low tide, which is locally known as '*Chhera Dwip*' (Separate Island). A total number of 54 interviewees were selected purposively to ensure the participation of all stakeholders including government employees; members of co-management committee; law enforcing agencies; volunteers; beach cleaners; turtle conservationists; food grain producers; union *Iparishad* (the local government system in the grass-root level); hotel and resort owners; restaurant managers; tour operators; shop keepers; fishermen; street vendors; rickshaw and van pullers; land purchasers and owners; boatman; cruise managers; and NGO workers.

According to the information provided by the local forest office, *Lalkakrar Char* is a part of *Gangamati* Reserved Forest, *Kuakata, Pataukhali* district. Deforestation, followed by fragmentation, created a few hundred-meter gaps from the current reserved forest's position. A total of 47 respondents were selected from the community on a random basis.

Dublar Char (*Dubla* Island) is located in the south-central part of the *Sundarbans* Reserved Forest under the *Sharankhola* range of the *Bagerhat* district. It is encircled by another four islands named as *Alorkole* (the lap of the light), *Majher Kella* (mid castle), *Office Kella* (the office of the castle) and *Meher Ali* (a person's name). The migratory artisanal and small-scale fishermen establish a temporary village in the winter season for fish catching and drying. Usually, the artisanal fishers harvest fish from the canals and rivers located in the sanctuaries, world heritage sites and *Ramsar* sites, while the small scale from the estuary and the territorial waters of the open sea. A total of 42 respondents were selected from the artisanal fishers' community randomly.

2.3.Data analysis

The content analysis was done by using the collected data, considering its uniqueness [30] in that it supports both qualitative [31] and quantitative analysis [32, 33], and can be used in both inductive and deductive ways. The content analysis helps a researcher to analyze the themes, concepts and interrelationships. The collected data were coded into different categories and variables. The study preferred a manifest content analysis rather than a latent content analysis to reflect the respondents' real views, avoiding any sorts of biases [34]. Four stages: de-contextualization, re-contextualization, categorization, and compilation were followed in the

content analysis [34]. The overlapping findings were not excluded from the results and discussions chapter to understand site and issue-specific scenarios differently. Images of artworks were used to present the key findings for better understanding the connections and interfaces, and to limit the number of words in this paper.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Bangladesh towards marine sustainability

3.1.1. Initiatives for unlocking the potential of marine resources

According to the secondary data collected from the SDG focal points, it is found that Bangladesh has made considerable progress towards the fortification of the institutional structures for harnessing the full utilization of marine-based potential resources, eyeing SDG 14 (**Table 1**).

Table 1: List of the protected areas in the coastal areas and the open sea

Institution	Initiatives
MOFA	Established a Maritime Affairs Unit (MAU) to prepare position papers to fix the maritime boundary with the neighbouring countries
MOEF	Appointed a focal point of the blue economy to coordinate with other divisions/ministries
MOS	Prepared a long-term and midterm strategic action plan for the extraction of marine resources
MPEMR	Structured a “Blue Economy Cell” to explore and extract mineral resources from the “Bay of Bengal
MOFL	Shaped a “Blue Economy Corner” to explore marine fisheries
Moedu/MOD	Established BSMRMU that has started its voyage with the maxim of providing skilled and knowledgeable human resources soon
MOST	Established BORI that has started walking and limping with the underdeveloped legs
Plandiv	Identified key the ministries/divisions in achieving SDG-14; incorporated the issues of increasing productive forest coverage in 7 th Five-Year Plan (2016-2020); prepared “Delta Plan 2100” to achieve economic and environmental sustainability by 2100
MPEMR	Established SREDA to explore alternative sources of energy (renewable) including blue energy
PMO	Formed a national coordination committee of marine resource extraction and management in 2014 through a gazette notification and appointing the “Principal Secretary to the PMO as the chief coordinator to monitor the action plans taken by different ministries and divisions

MOFA= Ministry of Foreign Affairs; MOFL= Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock; MOS= Ministry of Shipping; MPEMR=Ministry of Power, Energy and Minerals; MOEF= Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change; Plandiv=Planning Division; Moedu=Ministry of Education; MOD= Ministry of Defence; MOST= Ministry of Science and Technology; PMO= Prime Minister's Office; BORI=Bangladesh Oceanographic Research Institute; SREDA= Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority; BSMRMU=Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University

3.1.2. Establishing a network of protected areas

The *Ramsar* and world heritage sites, and most of the sanctuaries, encompassed mangrove ecosystems, while only the country's MPA aimed to conserve cetaceans in the submarine canyon and adjacent coastal waters (**Table 2**). The sanctuaries and the MPA followed the guidelines [35] provided by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). The ECAs were established to safeguard the marine zones, including coral reefs and mangroves, which have become critical due to the intensified anthropogenic disturbances.

Table 2: Characteristics of the protected areas in the coastal and marine areas

PAs	Name	Habitat type	Area covered	Established (Year)
WS	<i>Char Kukri-Mukri</i>	Offshore Island	40 ha	1981
WS	<i>Fashiakhali</i>	Offshore Island	1302 ha	2007
WS	<i>Teknaf</i>	Peninsula	11615 ha	2009
WS	<i>Tengragiri</i>	Mangrove	4049 ha	2010
WS	<i>Sonarchar</i>	Mangrove	2026 ha	2011
DS	<i>Chandpai</i>	Mangrove	560 ha	2012
DS	<i>Dhangmari</i>	Mangrove	340 ha	2012
DS	<i>Dudhmukhi</i>	Mangrove	170 ha	2012
WS	<i>Sundarban (East)</i>	Mangrove	122921 ha	2017
WS	<i>Sundarban (South)</i>	Mangrove	75310 ha	2017
WS	<i>Sundarban (West)</i>	Mangrove	119719 ha	2017
ECA	<i>Sundarbans</i>	Mangrove	292,926 ha	1999
ECA	St. Martin's	Coral Island	1,214 ha	1999
ECA	<i>Sonadia</i>	Offshore Island	10298 ha	1999
EP	<i>Kuakata</i>	Littoral forest	5661 ha	2005
MPA	Swatch-of-No-Ground	Marine	1,738 km ²	2014
RS	<i>Sundarbans</i>	Mangrove	601,700 ha	1992
NP	<i>Himchari</i>	Littoral Forests	1729 ha	1980
NP	<i>Kuakata</i>	Littoral Forest	1613 ha	2010
NP	<i>Nijhum Dwip</i>	Offshore Island	16345 ha	2001
WHS	<i>Sundarbans (South-western region)</i>	Mangrove	139,500 ha	1997

Also, the middle ground of the Bay of Bengal was identified as a safe breeding ground for fishery species inside the territorial water, and five sanctuaries in the inland rivers located in the tidal zone were declared as sanctuaries to protect the *hilsa (Tenuialosa ilisha)* fisheries from over-extraction.

3.1.3. Achieving SDG 14

No initiatives have been taken since 2016 to achieve the NPI (SDG 14.5.1). The actions taken by MOS, MOEF and MOFL resonated with four targets and an equal number of indicators of SDG 14 (**Table 3**). The coherent mechanism in curbing land-based pollutions seems shadowy. The project document of the “Sustainable Coastal and Marine Fisheries” endorses the cross-cutting issue (gender participation) at the cross-waters and a “whole society approach”. Four targets (14.2, 14.4, 14.5 and 14.6) out of 10 of SDG 14 are embedded with the “Aichi Biodiversity

Targets” to be achieved by 2020, which are partially reachable to Bangladesh, considering the time frame.

Table 3: Institutional actions in achieving SDG 14

<i>Target</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Ministry</i>	<i>Actions (during 2016-2019)</i>
14.1	14.1.1	MOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduced two waste-collecting ships • Established a waste treatment plant to manage waste originating from the lands • Purchased an oily water separator
		MOEF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased the number of "Effluent Treatment Plants (ETP)" to treat industrial wastewater
14.3	14.3.1	MOEF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measuring PH from four points located in the Chittagong division
14.4	14.4.1	MOFL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessing Marine Fisheries Resources
14.B.1	14.B.1	MOFL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing a project entitled “Sustainable Coastal and Marine Fisheries” • Established 03 fish landing centres with ancillary facilities in 03 coastal districts

3.2. Legal framework

To enunciate specific intentions to address environmental degradation and loss of biodiversity, Bangladesh has enacted many laws. The canvas of marine and coastal conservation is backed by many inland and sporadic marine laws. Besides, some minor acts and many archaic laws consist of ingredients of environmental protection and ecosystem management in general. A total of 23 laws support environmental protection directly, which are further supported by 185 laws indirectly [13].

3.2.1. Legislative measures

The respondents identified some key laws (**Table 4**) and major supportive laws (**Table 5**). The “Territorial Waters and Maritime Zones Act (TWMZ), 1974 discounts the concept of marine governance and does not accredit any specific ministry or department as the custodian of this law, though MOFA works on behalf of the government. MOFA drafted an amendment to the aforementioned act as “Bangladesh Maritime Zones Act, 2018”, which has been approved by the cabinet, but has not been ratified as a bill through the parliamentary process to date. This draft emphasizes the declaration and determination of the maritime zones and the control of criminal activities. The “Marine Fisheries Ordinance, 1983” pinpoints the regulations of marine fisheries (fish), overshadowing other living resources and conservation realms. The "Protection and Conservation of Fish Rules, 1985" are devised to protect the fish of inland water and coastal territorial water. The environment and conservation-related laws spotlight the conservation of inland biodiversity and environment, disregarding the open sea. “Bangladesh Biodiversity Act, 2017” and “Wildlife (Conservation and Security) Act, 2012” underlining the forest biodiversity somehow cover the obligations of CBD and “Aichi Biodiversity Targets”. “Bangladesh Environment Court Act, 2010”, accompanied by jurisdictional fuzziness, does not recognize the right of the common people directly.

Table 4: List of the key laws

Name	Key features
Territorial Waters and Maritime Zones Act 1974	Declared “Territorial Water”, “Contagious Zone”, “Economic Zone” and “Continental Shelf”, keeping the provisions of establishing “Conservation Zone” and taking measures against marine pollution if required
Marine Fisheries Ordinance 1983	Empowered DOF to regulate marine fisheries, fishing vessels and fishing gears; and provided a provision for establishing marine reserves outlining the destructive activities
Protection and Conservation of Fish Rules	Prohibited catching of certain fish during a certain period; and restricted destructive fishing, frog catching and other activities in freshwater and within coastal territorial water
Bangladesh Biodiversity Act 2017	Inculcated CBD by narrating the prohibited activities with the formation of different committees in enhancing conservation
Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act 1995	Pinpointed the conservation of biodiversity through ecosystem management and controlling pollution, and provided a provision of declaring ECAs for protecting highly degraded habitats; commissioned DOE to take measures against the emission of injurious smoke and environmental degradation
Wildlife (Conservation and Security) Act 2012	Cultivated a provision of declaring and managing different types of protected areas to enhance biodiversity conservation, and legitimized FD to regulate the fisheries within a sanctuary
Ecologically Critical Area Management Rules 2016	Restricted some activities, including alteration of the land category without prior permission of DOE in the ECAs, and legitimized the local governments and the community to be involved in the governance
Bangladesh Environment Court Act 2010	Outlined a provision of establishing one or more “Environment Court” in each division and district, and appointed the DOE as the prosecuting agency to punish the crimes related to environmental and social damage

“Bangladesh Merchant Shipping Ordinance, 1983” and “Bangladesh Flag Vessels (Protection) Ordinance, 1982” are not in accordance with the conventions of IMO, notably “International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL)”. Neither of the ordinances has been amended yet to incorporate the regulations of “Maritime Labour Convention, 2006” for maintaining the standards of seafarer living and working conditions.

Table 5: List of the associated laws

Name	Key features
Bangladesh Merchant Shipping Ordinance 1983	Provided the guidelines for maritime shipping, safety and registration procedures
Bangladesh Flag Vessels (Protection) Ordinance 1982	Outlined the penalties for violation of the maritime laws and for committing offences at sea
Bangladesh Ship Recycling Act 2018	Empowered the government to establish the Bangladesh Recycling Board for recycling ships, eyeing international conventions and guidelines

Bangladesh Oceanographic Research Institute Act 2015	Legitimized BORI in researching oceanography and to assess the environmental impact in marine realms
Weather Act 2018	Capacitated the Bangladesh Meteorological Department to prepare strategic action plans aligning with the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission and IMO
The protected areas of tourism and special tourism zone Act 2010	Enfranchised the government to identify the critical areas for restricting tourism
Bangladesh Water Act 2013	Provided the ownership of all sources of water, like sub-surface, marine, rainfall and atmosphere to the government
State Acquisition and Tenancy Act 1950	Appointed DC as the custodian of government-owned land and water, imposing restrictions on purchasing land by a bona fide cultivator for non-agricultural purposes.

Above all, the “Constitution of the People’s Republic of Bangladesh”, the supreme law of the country, added Article 18A in 2011 to guarantee the conservation of the environment and biodiversity [11]. This article was added in the section of "Fundamental Principles of the State Policy" without keeping any specific provisions that are judicially non-enforceable.

3.2.2. Non-compliance with the laws

In many cases, the public departments at the implementation level are reluctant to enforce laws, while the communities tend to violate the laws for various reasons (Figure 1). Proper enforcement of the laws is contingent upon the institutional capacity, good governance, political interventions, socioeconomic vulnerabilities and the level of awareness. Stereotypically, the responsibility for the enforcement of laws is dispensed to many public departments that pursue conflicts of interest, resulting in delayed or forestalled implementation. Frequently, the violators collect the information of the patrol campaigns in advance from a segment of enforcers who are involved in the racket [11].

Figure 1: The causes of non-compliances of the existing laws

3.3.The institutional framework

The regulatory jalousy of marine resource management relies on a bunch of ministries and their subordinate departments (**Table 6**). The line ministries formulate policy, allocate resources and approve projects and programmes, while the departments carry the load of implementation. Notably, MOEF, MOFL, MOS and MOFA play the pivotal roles in marine and coastal management. A little while back, Bangladesh adopted a “whole society approach” to integrate the views of relevant stakeholders from various levels in implementing SDGs.

3.3.1. Business allocation

MOS plays the key role in administering maritime transportation, where its principal business is 'port', a single word without further clarification that can encompass the lock, stock and barrel of various types of ports, including spaceports.

Table 6: List of the ministries or divisions involved in marine regulation directly or indirectly

M/D	Marine-related business
MOFA	The matters related to piracies and crimes committed on the high seas; promotion of the matters relating to continental shelf, territorial waters, contiguous zones and questions of fishery rights in the high seas and other questions of international law
MOFL	Aquaculture, including pearl culture, marine fisheries and brackish shrimp culture
MOS	Ports; maritime shipping, navigation; maritime safety, violation of sea laws, marine search and rescue, and marine pollution from ships and crafts; registration and safety administration of fishing vessels
MPEMR	Matters related to energy, mineral resources and geological survey
MOEF	Matters related to environment and ecology; environmental pollution; conservation of forests; afforestation; protection of wild birds and animals; and establishment of sanctuaries
MODMR	Overall disaster risk reduction and emergency response management, including relief, rehabilitation and safety net programmes
MOCAT	Legislation relating to tourism and registration of travel agencies
Minland	Rights in and over land and water, and management of government land, alluvial lands and unclassified state forest
Plandiv	All matters relating to statistics and informatics; maintenance of central geographical data; preparation of national plans, and the focal point of renewable sources of energy
MOWR	All matters relating to flood control, embankments, barrages, land reclamation, estuary control, anti-salinity measures, anti-desertification, and hydrological survey
MHA	Matters related to internal and border security
Moedu	Matters related to University education, technical education and educational research
MOD	Meteorological observations, hydrographic surveys and preparation of navigational charts
MOST	Matters relating to biotechnology and oceanographic science
Moind	Matters related to the salt industry
Mincom	Export policies; marketing of the agricultural products/animal products for export
MOA	Matters related to agricultural inputs, such as chemical fertilizer and pesticides
LGD	Administering local governments, maintenance of rural infrastructures
MSW	Community development with particular emphasis on a disadvantaged segment of

the society

M/D= Ministry/ Division; MODMR= Ministry of Disaster Management and Relief; MOCAT=Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism; Minland= Ministry of Land; MOWR=Ministry of Water Resources; MHA=Ministry of Home Affairs; Moind= Ministry of Industries; Mincom=Ministry of Commerce; MOA=Ministry of Agriculture; LGD=Local Government Division; Ministry of Social Welfare

The business allocations of MOFL and MOEF paid scarce attention to the conservation of the threatened species, coral reefs and critical areas. The MODMR is given the go-ahead with national risk reduction, evading coastal management, spatial planning and protection. The allocated business of MOCAT turns a blind eye to sustainable marine tourism or eco-tourism. Any words indicating marine and climate change do not float on the earmarked accreditation of MOEF, though it plays a key role in nature conservation and tackling climate change. The mandates of the newly formed MAU have not been included yet in the allocation of business of the MOFA. Only a few institutions established by the legal provisions are involved in marine conservation, but they are not entrusted with concrete mandates. The myriad institutions empowered by the "Rules of Business, 1996" work on marine resource management directly or indirectly, residing in different buttresses without an overarching framework and turning down relationship to one another. The above-mentioned cryptic mandates cannot put the seal on consistency and cohesion.

3.3.2. Jurisdictional overlapping

Many areas were identified where jurisdictions overlap with more than one ministry or division (**Figure 2**). The presence of bubbles and dots in the mandates given by the rules of business devises these crossroads. Furthermore, the legal framework legitimizes various departments to work on the same issue incongruously. MOEF enjoys hegemony over MOFL in regulating living resources, including fisheries in the protected areas, although MOFL is authorized to manage both freshwater and marine fisheries. The core issues of environmental protection are crisscrossed by MOEF, MOS, MOFL, MOA, Moind, LGD and MOST with inconclusive jurisdictions. These interfaces curb biodiversity conservation, environmental protection, coordination development, integration and cohesion, and proper law enforcement. In many cases, pillow throwing at each other, conflict of interests and even rivalry emerge from the points of intersection. The conflict of interests among various public institutions leads to fragmented "sector-by-sector" and "use-by-use" management policies [36].

Figure 2: Areas of jurisdictional overlap

3.4. Policy and strategic planning frameworks

In Bangladesh, there is no clear marine policy, but a few scattered policies formulated by the concerned line ministries cover various components of marine and coastal conservation. Bangladesh formulated the “National Environmental Policy 2018” with the motto of maintaining a balance between development and environmental protection to achieve SDGs. This policy focuses on establishing a green belt through the plantation in the coastal areas; controlling oil spillage in the mangrove; monitoring the marine environment; managing new accredited islands; tackling climate change through adaptation and mitigation, and ecotourism. The “National Shipping Policy 2000” strives to expand the development of seaports and inland shipping, and overlooks the environmental and conservation issues. Contradictorily, the “National Fisheries Policy 1998” encourages and discourages the shrimp and finfish culture in the coastal and mangrove areas at the same time. This policy gives only small-scale fishermen access in the shallow coastal areas (within 40- meter depth) and emphasizes the conservation of spawning grounds in the sea for natural breeding. In contrast, marine fishing in Bangladesh is concentrated in the shallow waters due to a lack of capacity and technologies [36]. These three policies include a bunch of public departments without spelling out the responsibilities, monitoring and evaluation tools, and a coordination mechanism. In Bangladesh, the public policy rarely brings out positive results due to formulaic and implementation dilemmas like political supremacy, bureaucratic superiority and inertia, influences of the donors, inadequate research, institutional complexities, ambiguous guidelines and the absence of line experts’ opinions [37]. Furthermore, the “National biodiversity strategy and action plan of Bangladesh 2016-2021” underscores the

importance of biodiversity conservation, notably inland biodiversity. The newly approved "Delta Plan 2100", a long-term strategy for this ongoing century prioritizes adaptive management practices to cope with the challenges emerging from anthropogenic-climatic stressors. This plan stresses using a holistic approach along with equitable water governance to achieve long-term food and water security, economic growth and environmental sustainability. The synchronization of harnessing the potentials and the biodiversity conservation of the Bay of Bengal is fizzled out in this plan.

3.5. The current scenarios of the conservation initiatives

To find the treasure troves in the protected and reserved areas and to get to the bottom of the aforementioned question, the major findings of the case studies have been unveiled here.

3.5.1. Joymonirghol

The protected areas of *Sundarbans* face an onslaught of threats like wildlife poaching, destructive fishing, encroachment, illegal logging and oil spillage (**Figure 3**). Fishing with poison endangers the survival of the endangered aquatic species, including cetaceans like the *Gangetic* Dolphin and *Irrawady* Dolphin. Wildlife, especially spotted deer and tiger poaching, and human-tiger conflicts, are reckoned as the incremental threats [38]. But despite several laws, institutional setup, policies and management plans, this unique mangrove shows crystal traces of degradation due to lack of coordination among the key role players. The co-management practices in the ECAs of *Sundarbans* go haywire, representing a multi-coloured picture. Different hierarchical co-management committees are assorted with the saints and devils safeguarding the domination of local politicians, elite class and vested interests, and overshadowing the effective participation of the community on an equal basis [39]. On some occasions, the co-management remains in a vegetative state when a segment of overseers is either orchestrating or patronizing the destructive activities.

Figure 3: Regulatory problems associated with illegal logging, destructive fishing and wildlife poaching

3.5.2. *Lalkar Char*

Lalkar Char is under threat after introducing motorbikes and mechanized vans for carrying tourists in the beach areas (**Figure 4**). The digging behaviour of this crab augments the oxygenation in the beach soil, accelerating the decomposition of organic matter and helping bioturbation [40]. The residing holes of this little mermaid on the beach are destroyed by the motorcyclist and van drivers, causing death and injury. The increased abundance of jellyfish can be linked to increased eutrophication, turbidity and hypoxia originating from anthropogenic stressors [41]. The plantation of exotic *Acacia* (*Acacia mangium*) and *Eucalyptus* (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis*) beside the beach without assessing the environmental consequences indicates a dearth of coordination among practitioners, researchers, academicians and the community. The conflict of interests and exercising the jurisdictional authorities are oblivious in the underdeveloped beach apart from tourism amenities.

Figure 4: Regulatory problems associated with the red crab conservation

3.5.3. Saint Martin Island

The coral species, globally endangered turtles, associated fish species and migratory birds are threatened by the escalation of human pressures like destructive fishing and boating; over-extraction of living resources; uncontrolled tourism and waste disposals; and use of antifouling agents, chemical fertilizers and pesticides (**Figure 5**). The co-management approach goes awry due to scarce coordination among public departments, law enforcers, *Union Parishad* (local government at the grassroots level), NGOs, tour operators, volunteers, conservationists, and hotel resort and restaurant owners.

Figure 5: Regulatory problems associated with coral and other threatened species conservation

3.5.4. Dublar char

The artisanal fisher's community is threatened by the security, economic, political and social vulnerabilities (**Figure 6**). This sector remains in the doldrums due to a policy implementation gap and ineffective law enforcement [42]. Piracy and robbery constitute the major threat to the life and profession of artisanal fishers. The foreign pirates mount sudden attacks, looting fish and other valuable items. Local pirates are sometimes involved in the kidnapping and killing of the fishers. Respondents reported that the law enforcers are not proactive in controlling piracy. They do not have any formal channel to obtain a loan to improve their fishing techniques and utilise technology such as modern boats, nets, and other necessary equipment. These artisanal fishers must, therefore, depend on *Dadan* and *Mahajan*. This study learned from the respondents that the fishers only receive 30% of the actual prices due to a complex market chain. The fish stocks in the shallow water declined drastically due to invasions of the commercial fishers, whose practices push the artisanal fishers back to the coast.

Figure 6: Regulatory problems associated with artisanal fisheries

The high rate of degradation of the protected and conserved areas raises questions about the efficacy of the regulatory schemes. The myriad instruments and many fora regulating the marine and coastal living resources can be considered nearly futile. Therefore, the declaration of a protected area is not a panacea, but overcoming the associated pitfalls is a matter of concern. It can be argued that conservations and degradations go hand in hand, indicating that declaration of a protected area cannot fasten the conservation until and unless proper regulation is ensured. Surprisingly, the paramouncy of degradation overruns, showing the level of competencies of the legal and institutional acclimation. It is an undeniable fact that no convincing maps of the protected areas could be collected; consequently, it can be argued that intensity was given on declaration rather than implementation. Both the *Hilsa* fishermen community and the DOF have a long history of face-offs to shift the border of the sanctuaries, a poorly or non-drawn line of actual control separating restricted and open areas [1, 15].

Except for the inland *hilsa* sanctuaries, the reimbursement of other protected areas is gloomy due to the aforementioned controversies, political hegemony and socioeconomic hot water [1]. The aftermath effects of the conservation initiatives for *Hilsa* are alloyed with the enhanced protection and some negative socio-economic consequences [1, 11, 15]. The initiatives could not garner sufficient support from the community for disregarding their poverty. Furthermore, incremental unfair political intrusion at the implementation level is emerging as a hegemon, worsening the scenarios [1, 11, 15, and 43]. If true that the marine governance is inoperative as a consequence of the absence of an integrated and holistic regulatory framework [44].

3.6. Can Bangladesh combat the emerging challenges of anthropogenic climate change with the existing regulatory framework?

The key informants classified the challenges emanating from the human-climatic stressors into three categories, considering the time-series effects: historical (flooding and circadian cyclones), emerging (increased salinity, marine pollution and brackish shrimp culture) and future (ocean acidification and sea-level rise). Unanimity was observed in seeing the frailty of the current institutional, legal and policy framework to overcome those challenges. The ocean acidification and increased water temperature in Bangladesh are not visible despite showing a non-significant increasing trend of water temperature and a decreasing trend of pH from 2000 to 2012 [45]. The *Sundarbans* delta may confront the projected sea-level rise by accumulating the river sediments originating from the Himalaya.

3.6.1. Increased salinity

Increased salinization jeopardizes the vertical and horizontal forest structure, composition and species richness through erasing fresh swamps, alterations of plant species and facilitating the colonization of salt-loving invasive species. This challenge was pondered as a silent disaster for the *Sundarbans* mangrove as well as for Bangladesh. The dominant and pioneer plant species, *Sundari* (*Heritiera fomes*), which suffered from “Top Dying Disease”, is being replaced by *Keora* (*Sonneratia apetala*), adding no economic value [49]. Consequently, the denotation of the *Sundarbans* stemming from the *Sundari* tree will go over to “*Keorabans*”. *Hanthal* (*Phoenix paludosa*) and *Golpata* (*Nypa fruticans*), indicator palm species of this mangrove, are struggling with the increased salinity for the continuation [47]. Salinization going hand in hand with anthropogenic stressors and frequent cyclones, opens the door for the opportunist and salt-tolerant invasive species [46, 48]. To date, Bangladesh has not developed any coherent and integrated policy to overcome this challenge scrutinizing the key stakeholders and discrete mandates of the disbanded institutional arrays. The survival of this mangrove depends on the regulation of freshwater resources together with the conservation of biodiversity [50].

Figure 7: Regulatory problems associated with increased salinity

3.6.2. Tiger prawn culture

The brackish shrimp culture in the *Sundarbans* areas has exacerbated the socioeconomic, environmental and agro-ecological vulnerabilities through putting an end to agricultural activities, fuelling the salinization, propagating climate refugees and augmenting inequalities (**Figure 8**). The direct, indirect and associated challenges cannot be kept down as the lionine

shrimp farmers modulate local politics and economy mostly. Thereupon, once in a while, they are ready to buckle up the laws and guidelines, and substantially they are unchallenged by the absenteeism of holistic policies and fragile coordination among public departments. Bangladesh could not meet the “FAO Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries” in brackish aquaculture despite signing in 1995 [51]. The article 9.1 of this code of conduct calls for developing a competent legal and administrative framework for maintaining ecosystem integrity, rational use of resources to enhance ecological sustainability, unafflicting the livelihoods of the community, and minimizing the adverse effects.

Figure 8: Regulatory problems associated with brackish tiger prawn culture

3.6.3. Marine Pollution

Though Bangladesh is not a heavily industrialized country, marine pollution occurs here, encompassing various types of pollutions originated from the land and the Bay (**Figure 9**). Oil spillage occurring from the accidents of oil tankers and pollutants discharged from the shipbreaking industries are considered the leading causes of marine pollution. Bangladesh, one of the top three countries in terms of shipbreaking and recycling, releases different types of waste every year, which affects the coastal and marine environment [17]. In 2014, approximately 357664 litres of furnace oil were spilt into 80 km of canals and rivers of the *Sundarbans* mangrove from an oil tanker accident. Instant mortality of many phytoplankton, zooplankton, crustaceans, seaweeds, and the seedlings of *Sundari* and *Gewa* tree (*Excoecaria agallocha*) was reported [52]. ‘The International Convention on Oil Pollution Preparedness, Response, and

Cooperation 1990' focuses on oil pollution emergency plans, immediate actions and assessment of environmental impacts. Virtually the control of land-based pollutions is unattainable due to the presence of multi-layered authorities given by many fragmented and scattered laws. Article 207 of UNCLOS emphasizes the regulatory and legal framework to control land-based pollutions. Different articles of UNCLOS and MARPOL remind the adoption of a regulatory and legal framework to control marine pollution from the maritime vessels; the guidelines for dumping in the sea; and the establishment of transboundary marine governance. Bangladesh has not amended any outlier laws, framed policies and established marine governance to protect the coastal and marine ecosystems from marine pollution [17].

Figure 9: Regulatory problems associated with marine pollution

4. Recommendations

In regards to overcoming the challenges, several recommendations were amassed from the respondents. The propositions encompass reallocation of business, legal reforms, formulating evidence-based marine policy and farsighted strategic planning; and reduction of the dependencies on living resources.

4.1.1. Business reallocation:

Insistence was given on establishing sectoral governance through amending “the Rules of Business” to abolish jurisdictional overlapping and conflict of interest, and to make sure that one’s business is not everyone’s business (**Figure 10**). A few respondents stressed on creating a separate ministry on oceanography and some statutory bodies to build strong coordination and integration mechanisms among the ministries. There was a solid consensus that the local governments should be responsible for the day-to-day maintenance of the beaches and amenities, and regulating beach-based tourism and protection. The local governments will foster

community partnership, community education, planning for the environment, landscape protection, conservation of wildlife, water resource management, waste management and recycling in the beach areas. MOFA should take initiatives to establish high sea governance with other marine states shared by the Bay of Bengal, following UNCLOS, to address transboundary conservation. The artisanal fishers urged to modernize the market chain by clearing the intermediary group and to provide loans from the formal banking sector.

Figure 10: Recommended reallocation of business for different ministries or divisions

4.2. Legal reforms

Two options: amendment of the existing laws or enactment of new laws were couched side by side in the arguments (**Figure 11**). Both these options gave prominence to the abolishment of jurisdictional overlapping and the inclusion of international obligations. Attention was given to the proper enforcement of the existing laws until and unless they are amended or new laws are enacted. The respondents advocated for the capacity building of the public departments at the implementation level and the incorporation of ethical education in their training programmes.

Figure 11: Recommended legal reforms and ways of proper enforcement of the existing laws

4.3. An evidence-based national marine policy

Based on the respondents' suggestions, a conceptual model of an evidence-based national marine policy has been developed, focusing on the conservation of marine living resources and environmental protection (**Figure 12**). The respondents also stressed the adoption of a systematic approach, moving beyond the traditional practices in formulating the policy. The opinions of the sectoral experts, academicians and researchers may inculcate a holistic policy framework. National strategic planning should be formed to combat the emerging challenges as well as the projected future challenges.

Figure 12: A conceptual model of an evidence-based national marine policy

4.4. Alternative income generations

The respondents advocated many alternative income-generating activities to reduce dependency on the living resources, especially of the *Sundarbans* mangrove, and to avoid brackish shrimp culture (**Figure 13**). The combination of crab caging and giant freshwater prawn (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) culture by reserving or harvesting the rainwater may be equally profitable as brackish culture. The *Sundarbans* Mangrove is a heaven of honeybees due to providing a year-round supply of nectar, pollen and water; and for protection from storms. *Sundarbans* has a natural resilience against forest fires, and it naturally deters termites and ants. World-famous lotus honey is produced from the tree species, *Khalsi* (*Aegiceras corniculatum*). Apiculture farming can be considered an alternative income-generating activity for the community residing in the ecologically critical areas. By utilizing the traditional knowledge and practices, the honey collector-folk collect crude honey and wax from the deep forest of *Sundarbans*. The traditional honey collection practices kill a significant portion of the bee community, including the queen. The crude honey is mixed with raw wax, plant debris, pollens and larvae of a bee. Consequently, crude honey follows a fermentation process in a very short time [53]. Scientific apiculture will help in the development of the agro-industry and the conservation of bees.

Figure 13: Recommended alternative income-generating activities avoiding brackish shrimp culture

5. Conclusion

At the commencement of SDGs, Bangladesh streamlined action plans in achieving social, economic and environmental sustainability. At the same time, the government is committed to exploiting the coastal and marine resources to become a developed nation by 2041. SDGs cannot be achieved in conjunction with the incremental degradation of habitats and ecosystems. Social and economic sustainability cannot be ensured without environmental sustainability. Ironically, environmental sustainability policies are disregarded day after day. The existence of the last adobes of marine biodiversity will not be safeguarded without legal and institutional reforms and the framing of a national marine policy. Bangladesh needs farsighted strategic planning instead of myopic or piecemeal approaches to combat emerging environmental challenges and the forthcoming challenges like ocean acidification and sea-level rise. The *Sundarbans*, the green shield against the circadian cyclones, draws quick and robust attention for its survival. The unfair political intrusion in the implementation level of public departments cripples the proper implementation of laws and policies. Bangladesh has adopted a “whole society approach” in implementing SDGs. The active participation of the community on an equal basis and strengthening the local government bodies can be a giant leap for good governance. The carrot and stick motivation theory may change the current scenarios of the institutional framework. Uprooting all barriers to ensuring environmental justice may help in healing degradation and destruction.

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